

REDUCING THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON FOOD SECURITY AND AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. Prezident Sh.Mirziyoyev has declared a law about development and implementation of state policy on food security. It is aimed at Ensuring food safety and improving the diet and producing the required amount of food. According to the resolution, a strategy for agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 has been developed.

Keywords: Climate change, environmental problem, agriculture, soil erosion, drought, famine, global warming, ecological stress, greenhouse effect.

Аннотация. Президент Ш.Мирзиёев объявил закон о разработке и реализации государственной политики в области продовольственной безопасности. Она направлена на обеспечение безопасности пищевых продуктов, улучшение рациона питания и производство необходимого количества продуктов питания. Согласно постановлению разработана стратегия развития сельского хозяйства Республики Узбекистан на 2020-2030 годы

Ключевые слова: Изменение климата, экологическая проблема, сельское хозяйство, эрозия почвы, засуха, голод, глобальное потепление, экологический стресс, парниковый эффект.

It is known that Uzbekistan is a country with great potential and opportunities to grow the most delicious and healthy fruits and vegetables in the world. Consequently, the unique soil and climatic conditions of our country, the average number of sunny days in the country is 320 days a year, the gradual change of four seasons create favorable conditions for the cultivation of a wide range of high quality fruits and vegetables.

In recent years, the country's agricultural sector is being reformed, in particular, the system of public administration in this sector has been improved. The widespread introduction of market relations, to strength the legal framework of relations between agricultural producers, processors and sellers, to attract investment in agriculture and to provide manufacturers with modern equipment are in the process of organization.

At the same time, there is no any long-term strategy for agricultural development. Subsequently, it has a bad impact on the effective use of land and water resources, attracting investment in the sector, generating high incomes for producers, and increasing product competitiveness.

It announced a "current 40-day" planting date until December 10. The project plans to increase urban green space from the current 8% to 30% by planting 200 million trees and shrubs a year. The main goal of this project is to prevent various climate changes. Because today, climate change is causing a variety of global problems. One of them is food problems.

The world's population is growing every year. At the beginning of the XXI century, the population of our planet has exceeded 6 billion. Everyone needs to consume 100-120 g of protein a day to live a normal life. However, the daily protein intake of most people does not exceed 50-60 g. There is also a lack of fatty and carbohydrate nutrients necessary for human life. One of the main tasks facing humanity today is to solve theoretical and practical problems aimed at meeting

food needs. According to the United Nations, 815 million people are currently starving, and by 2050 that number will reach 2 billion people. 12.9% of them live in developing countries. Forty-five percent of deaths among children under the age of five are due to malnutrition. Today, 3.1 children die every year as a result of starvation. Food security is one of the most pressing challenges facing countries around the world. The United Nations also says that today is the time to radically change the approach to food production and distribution.

So far, ideally the village, Forests and fisheries are able to provide food and create a source of income for world population people. Moreover, in this case, agriculture can be developed and measures to protect the environment can be implemented. What is the main cause of climate change? Experts say that the main factor in climate change is the greenhouse effect. The accumulation and stagnation of heat from the sun at ground level is called the greenhouse effect. That is, light from the sun is sent back to space by the earth's atmosphere. Some of these rays are absorbed into various gases emitted by humans instead of going out into space. When it does not return to space, the earth heats up and forms a greenhouse layer that affects the climate. Climate change and agriculture. Climate change and agriculture are interrelated processes, both of which occur on a global scale, and their negative impact on climate change is directly related to agriculture. Extreme changes in temperature, precipitation, climate, pests, diseases and atmosphere have a negative impact on the quality of food. Another side of the issue. Agriculture is the largest employer in the world. Today, 40 percent of the world's population lives on this sector. It is a major source of income and employment for families in poor villages. In developing countries, five million small farms, mostly dry, providing 80 percent of the food supply. Therefore, investing in this area will increase the country's ability to supply food to local and foreign markets, as well as ensure food security.

According to most agronomists, agricultural production is mainly affected by the intensity and speed of climate change, but also by the gradual trends of the climate.

If the change is gradual, then there may be enough time. Rapid climate change can damage agriculture in most countries, especially in countries with very poor soil and climatic conditions.

Most observed effects:

1. Sliding in precipitation mode: longer periods of heavy rain and drought.
2. Increase in average temperature: summer heat and winter warming can affect plant cycles and lead to early flowering, less pollination and frost damage.
3. Increased flooding: leads to crop damage, water pollution, soil erosion.
4. Increased drought rate: affects plant survival and increases the risk of forest fires.
5. Degraded soils: Monoculture planting systems make the soil less organic and prone to erosion and water pollution.

Climate change has a number of negative consequences in Uzbekistan:

Decreased soil moisture increases the risk of repeated droughts and decreases productivity;

The reduction in the flow of water into the Aral Sea is accelerating the desertification of the river delta and the emergence of new desert areas on the dried seabed; which increases dust in large areas of atmospheric air;

Changes in anomalous events, such as heating and cooling, are leading to the destruction of agricultural products and fruits.

Conclusion

The fact that climate change is deteriorating year by year can be attributed to the fact that humanity continues to use the Earth cruelly. In many countries, this process is seen as the biggest threat to security.

Tragic events around the world should give a strong enough impetus to the development of additional mechanisms for environmental security. Otherwise, it may be too late.

The United Nations has recently launched another initiative in this area. In other words, a global campaign has been launched to combat food waste. This also serves food security. According to the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), 1.3 billion tons of food is thrown away each year throughout the whole planet. (In a sense, we are contributing to this wasting by celebrating different types of celebrations, such as weddings. Some effort is being made to reduce such activities in vain). I think that in order to put an end to such a waste of resources, it is important to change the conditions of their storage.

REFERENCES

1. www.Ziyo. net.
2. D.F. Muqimov , D.R. G'ofurov. „Oziq ovqat xafsizligi” 2003.
3. M.Mamajonov. <Iqlim omillari>1999.
4. D.A. Qodirov SH.A Shokirov ,Qishloq xo'jaligida antropogen omillar'T2008.y